

GROWTH PROCESSES OF THE POPULATION OF THE COUNTRIES OF THE WORLD, POPULATION DYNAMICS.

Dilshoda Inomjonova

Andijan State University

a student of geography at the

Faculty of Natural Sciences

dilshodainomjonova20@gmail.com

Annotation: *This article covers about the development of socio-economic and cultural life of society, the total population of the regions of the world, the formation of sinfiy society, the preservation of feudal and primitive society relations, developing countries.*

Key words: *politics, economic, production, cultural centers, areal, birth, death, feudal, primitive, epidemic.*

Further improvement of the productive forces led to the emergence of classes and states among the population. Society astasekin moved from the primitive system to the era of slavery (sinfiy society). The socio-economic and cultural life of the society began to develop. These changes in the development of society were much faster than in the era of the primitive system of the population. The main reason for this is the high birth rate. And the higher the birth rate, in turn, was bog1, with the entry of women into early marriage, the

withdrawal of childbirth, as well as the support of polygamy by the people, state and religion. But during the period of the slavery regime, the mortality rate among the population was much higher. The reason is that in many rural and urban areas there is a wide spread of infectious diseases due to the extremely dense settlement of the population and the lack of hygienic and sanitary conditions. The development of culture among the population led to the emergence of centers of ancient civilization. These cultural centers were formed in

Results of National Scientific Research

irrigated areas of the Earth's Kurra (Egypt, Mesopotamia, India, China and other regions). It is estimated that during the time of the Pharaohs in ancient Egypt lived 7 million inhabitants. The total population in the regions of the world was around 5 million in 30 thousand years BC awalgi. During this period, the current areals of population settlement appeared on earth. The struggle of man for survival led to positive (progressive) changes in the development of society. As the production forces began to develop, people first switched to livestock, and then to peasant farming, began to fight against hunger, diseases. Now they work, create material goods. Craftsmanship, trade developed and cities began to appear. These positive changes in human life will improve their living conditions.

Sinfiy the formation of society, the differences in socio-economic and cultural development in the regions of the world, directly affected the process of reproduction of the population. In some regions the mortality among the population caused by the frontline

epidemics and urushlar was incredibly high, the villages remained unpopular. For this period, in the case of repeated reproduction of the population, a common feature, as in primitive society, was preserved - the high birth rate. As in the system of slavery, many childhood was supported not only by traditions, but also by Public Policy, religion, especially Islam and Hinduism. The first "cultural and technical revolution" in the history of human development led to the further development of productive forces. The production of food products developed. And this phenomenon, in turn, led to an increase in the number of inhabitants of the world. At the beginning of our era, the population of the Earth's sphere was 200-250 million. the man was around. As already mentioned above, the main part of the population is located in the Roman Empire, China and India. In the XII-XV centuries, the M aium part of the world's population was exterminated due to the large urushlar. Especially from these wars, the population of the countries of Eastern and South-Eastern Europe suffered

great losses. Urushlar not only did it lead to direct extinction of the population, but also to premature eye chores from life because of the famine that occurred on account of the farm, the disruption of production. If in the first 500-ies (100500500-ies) the population of the earth increased by 135 million, then in 1500-1750-ies or 250-ies this figure was 288 million, that is, the population growth accelerated by 2 times. Since the second half of XVIII asming, population growth has accelerated even more. If we look at the increase in the world population from 1000 to 2005 year, the fastest growing period of the population is the XX century. In 1900-1950-ies, the population of the Earth's sphere increased by an average of 0,90% every year, while in 1950-2000-ies, the exchanger reached 1,75%. In the early years of the 21st century, the rate of increase in the number of world population was somewhat slowed down. In 2000-2009, the average annual rate of the world population is 1.42%. In the current period (2017 y), more than 7,5 billion people are living on Earth.

There is a sharp discrepancy in the number of population by regions of the world. As a result, by the second half of the XX century and by the beginning of the XXI century, demographic problems with territorial features appeared on our planet. In some states, the number of population in relation to the production of material wealth has increased very rapidly, causing the problem of "population growth", while in some regions there is a sharp decline in the birth rate of the population, that is, as a result of the decrease in the demographic criterion, the problem of "demographic aging" is observed. "The problems of population reproduction are observed mainly in developing countries. The increase in the world population is also almost synonymous with these states. In 1967, the population of the Earth's sphere increased by 65 million. Of this, 56 million occurred on account of an increase in the population of developing countries. Such a rapid increase in the world population was explained by scientists as "demographics". In developing countries, such a rapid population

growth in the second half of the twentieth century was largely due to three demographic factors. The first of them is the fact that the birth is kept at a high level. In 1950 - 1966, the number of children born in the world compared to each 1000 population of Economically Developed Countries of Europe, North America and Japan amounted to 16-22, while in developing countries this figure was 35-45, and even in some states in Africa 50-60. It is connected with the level of socio - economic development of births. In developing countries, on the one hand, the preservation of the relations of feudal and primitive society, on the other hand, the long domination of the colonial system caused the ulama to remain as economically undeveloped agrarian regions of the world, as a result of which the industry will develop. The main part of the population lives in villages. And the rural lifestyle is one of the main factors leading to the high incidence of births. In addition, the social inequality of ayollama, the extreme low level of literacy of the population, the presence of traditions

that support polygamy in a number of Muslim countries, the means of preventing pregnancy and the lack of widespread understanding about them have led to the high birth rates of the population in developing countries.

The second demographic factor that causes an increase in the population of developing countries is a sharp decrease in population mortality. Statistics show that in developing countries the number of people who read in 1950-th year compared to every 1000 people was 15 - 22, in 1965-th year this figure was 8 - 10. Especially in children, the OI has sharply decreased. For example, in Venezuela-81, Guatemala - 107, Ecuador - 110, Egypt - 153 of the children born every 1000 in 1950, boisa, in 1965, these figures, in accordance with the established procedure 48; 93; 93 and 118. In other words, in developing countries, the population decreased by 1,15 times in the 1950 - 1965 years. Such a short-term sharp decline in the population's GDP, as noted above, is largely due to the decrease in the incidence of various epidemics and infectious diseases, resulting from the

provision of medical care to the population by the UN and other charitable organizations in developing countries. The third factor that has led to an increase in the number of people in developing countries is the rise in the average life expectancy of the population. For example: in India, which ranks second in the world in terms of population, the average life

expectancy in 1950-year was -3.7 in women, in men - 32.4 in men, in 1960-year, the life expectancy of women was extended to 9 years and 40.5, in 2009-65. In 1950 - 1960-ies, the life expectancy of men increased to 9.5 years and amounted to 41.9, and in 2017-70 years. Such a case can also be observed in Africa, Latin America and Asia in a number of countries.

Available publications:

1. POPULATION AND SOCIETY: An Introduction to Demography Dudley L. Poston, Jr. 3-p. :
2. Soliev A.S. Theoretical and practical issues of my economic geography.-Т., 1999.В.48. Failure to take migration into account within 7 is also a mistake. Reason
- 3 Ионцева В.А. Экономика народонаселения демография.-М.,2002.С.33.
- 4 Борисов В. А. Демография. — М.: NOTABENE, 1999, 2001. С.5.
5. Tajieva ZN. Regional characteristics of demographic processes in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Doctoral dissertation.- Т., 2017. В. 17.
6. Z.N. Tajiyeva F. A. Do'smonov Demography Tashkent - 2020 "Innovascular History of the World"
7. Richard S. Kratmich, A.E.Luloff, Donald R.Field. People, Places and Landscapes. Utah.USA.2011. MaziTiun- the essence was taken advantage of.